

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

STX4 (Syntaxin-4)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

Gene ID / UniProt ID / EC	6810 / Q12846 / -
Target Nominator	TREAT-AD, AMP-AD
TREAT-AD Authors	Emore-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD center
Therapeutic Area(s)	Alzheimer's disease
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Validated antibodies & generic knockout cell lines: YCharOS antibody characterization report

Protein constructs & expression methods: Coiled-coil domain of STX4A (M1-L275) containing an N-terminal His6-Sumo1-Sumo cleavage site tag.

TARGET SOURCE & HYPOTHESIS

Why was the target selected? This target was identified through a protein quantitative trait locus analysis.

TREAT-AD Overall Score: 3.45 (rank #4782)

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics, genetics, and literature evidence. The Overall Score represents the gene target's general relevance to Alzheimer's Disease, and is the sum of the target's Genetics Score, Genomics Score, and Literature Score. Overall Score values range from 0 to 7, with 7 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology

used to calculate these scores is available [here](#). This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v33.

The TREAT-AD Overall score for this target is 3.45 out of 7 (rank #4782). The individual score components include 1.65 of 3 for genetics, 1.80 out of 2 for genomics, and 0 out of 2 for literature recency. The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of STX4, both protein and RNA, is significantly increased in brains from patients with AD.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains). These biological domains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biological domains via GO term annotations. STX4 is annotated to GO terms primarily from the Myelination, Autophagy, and Synapse biological domains.

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell expression data from the Allen Brain Institute. The distribution of expression values for all genes found in each broad cell type are displayed as violins, points indicating the expression of the target in specific subtypes within each broad class including a label for the highest expressing cell type for each broad class. These data indicate that STX4 is expressed in excitatory and inhibitory neurons along with oligodendrocytes in healthy adult brains.

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

Syntaxin 4 (STX4) is a synaptic protein that is involved in exocytosis that is implicated in TREAT-AD informatics analysis as a potential novel AD-linked gene. However, despite the identification of several potentially linked disease related processes, little is known about STX4 in AD progression, or what role it may play in driving or forestalling disease progression. In order to facilitate future investigations into STX4 role in AD, we are developing a target enabling package for STX4 consisting of purified protein and validated STX4 antibodies for general use by the scientific community. The goal is that by generating and sharing resources for the study of STX4, we will promote further studies in AD biology involving STX4, SNARE protein complex role in AD, and an exploration of how STX4 may fit into future therapeutic or biomarker identification studies of AD.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

Syntaxin 4 (STX4) is a component of the SNARE complex (along with VAMP2 and SNAP23) that promotes trans golgi network (TGN) to plasma membrane (PM) vesicle fusion (1). The facilitation of vesicles from the TGN to the cell surface promotes exocytosis for vesicular content into the extracellular space, and is associated with regions of synaptic activity in neurons that may promote synaptic plasticity (2,3). STX4 is implicated as a Parkinson's disease (PD) risk gene from combined multiomic studies coordinately examining GWAS risk loci and functional expression changes (4). One element of PD risk may be conferred through SNARE protein release of alpha-synuclein, driving the transfer of pathogenic protein transfer, as recent studies report (5). STX4 regulated exocytosis may play a role in diabetic pancreatic beta-islet cells release of insulin, and dysfunction may exacerbate diabetic lack of insulin regulation (6,7). Further, STX4 was recently identified as a peripheral skeletal muscle insulin resistance remediation factor by facilitating the activation of DRP1, and the restoration of mitochondrial viability in skeletal muscle (8). This suggests that STX4 may play regulatory roles in vesicle trafficking and fusion beyond just exocytotic release at the plasma membrane that may facilitate mitochondrial function. TREAT-AD studies are converging on the significance of mitochondrial function in AD pathology and suggest that STX4 may play a role at multiple levels, or within a set of biological domains, that contribute to mediation of AD risk.

RESULTS – THE TEP

Validated Antibodies & Generic Knockout Cell Lines

The YCharOS Antibody Characterization Report guides researchers to select the most appropriate antibodies for STX4. The YCharOS antibody characterization pipeline uses knockout (KO) cells to perform head-to-head comparisons of available commercial antibodies for STX4 by immunoblot (Western blot), immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence. The cell line background was chosen based on the adequate expression of the target protein.

Complete report: [STX4 antibody characterization report](#)

Proteins Purified

STX4AA-c005: Coiled-coil domain of STX4A (M1-L275) containing an N-terminal His6-Sumo1-Sumo cleavage site tag. This protein will be useful for activity assays.

Fig. 1. SEC trace (left) of STX4AA-c005 with major peak fractions run on an SDS-PAGE gel (right).

CONCLUSION

The tools presented here provide a foundation for further biological investigation of the role of STX4 in AD.

FUNDING INFORMATION

The work performed by the Emory-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD Center has been funded by the National Institute on Aging through grant U54 AG065187.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Materials and Methods

Protein Constructs

Plasmids are available on addgene: <https://www.addgene.org/browse/article/28220285/>

Construct Details

Construct ID	STX4AA-c005
Parental vector	pSUMO-LIC
Tag	N-terminal His6-SUMO1-SUMO cleavage site
Protein mass (with tag)	44605.3 Da
Protein mass (with tag removed)	32045.3 Da
Extinction Coefficient ($M^{-1} cm^{-1}$)	8940
Protein sequence (with tag)	MCSSHHHHHHGSGSGSDQEAKPSTEDLGDKKEGEYIKLVIGQDSSEIHFKVKMTTHLKKLKESY CQRQGVPMNSLRFLFEGQRIADNHTPKELGMEEDVIEVYQEQTGGMRDRTHELRQGDDSSD EEDKERVALVVHPGTARLGSPDEEFFHKVRTIRQTIVKLGKVKQELEKQVVTILATPLPEESMKQEL QNLRDEIKQLGREIRLQLKAIEPQKEEADENYSVNTRMRKTQHGVLSSQQFVELINKCNSMQSEY REKNVERIRRQLKITNAGMVSDEELEQMLDSGQSEVFVSNILKDTQVTRQALNEISARHSEIQQL ERSIRELHDIFTFLATEVEMQGEMINRIEKNILSSADYVERGQEHVKTALENQKKARKKKVL
Protein sequence (after tag removal)	MRDRTHELRQGDDSSDEEDKERVALVVHPGTARLGSPDEEFFHKVRTIRQTIVKLGKVKQELEKQ QVVTILATPLPEESMKQELQNLRDEIKQLGREIRLQLKAIEPQKEEADENYSVNTRMRKTQHGVLSS QQFVELINKCNSMQSEYREKNVERIRRQLKITNAGMVSDEELEQMLDSGQSEVFVSNILKDTQV TRQALNEISARHSEIQQLERSIRELHDIFTFLATEVEMQGEMINRIEKNILSSADYVERGQEHVKTA LENQKKARKKKVL

Expression and Purification Protocol

Expression host	<i>E. Coli</i> : BL21(DE3)-R3-pRARE
Expression medium	Terrific broth (TB) with 50 µg/ml kanamycin (kan). Starter cultures also included 34 µg/ml chloramphenicol (cm).
Transformation and storage	Transform the construct into the <i>E. coli</i> strain BL21(DE3)-R3-pRARE, a phage-resistant variant of Rosetta 2 (MSD). Plate on LB-agar plates containing kan (50 µg/ml) and cm (34 µg/ml). Inoculate LB broth containing the same antibiotics with several colonies. After overnight incubation at 37°C, add glycerol to 15% (v/v) final volume, and store at -80°C.
Expression	Inoculate LB + kan + cm media for overnight growth at 37°C. Inoculate 1 L of TB + kan with 10 ml of the overnight culture. Grow cultures at 37°C with vigorous aeration in 2.5 L Tunair flasks until reaching an $OD_{600} = 1.5 - 2$. Shift the cultures to 18°C for 30 minutes before inducing protein expression with 0.3 mM IPTG. Continue incubation for 16 hours at 18°C before harvesting cells by centrifugation (3000g, 25 min, 4°C).

	Store pellets and -80°C until needed.
Purification buffers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lysis buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 10 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 2. W30 Buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 30 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 3. Elution Buffer (EB): 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 300 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP. 4. SEC buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 5. Ni-sepharose beads, equilibrated in Lysis buffer.
Purification step 1: IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Resuspend thawed pellet in lysis buffer (40 ml/L of original culture). Lyse cells by sonication on ice (20 min, 5 s on, 10 s off, 35% amplitude) with occasional stirring. 2. Centrifuge the lysate (25 min, 67000g, 4°C). Decant the supernatant. 3. Add 0.6 ml of Ni-sepharose beads to lysate in a 50-ml falcon tube. Mix by rotation for 1 hr in a cold room. 4. Spin lysate with Ni-sepharose beads (700g, 5 min, 4°C). Decant lysate and wash beads with 100 ml Lysis buffer. Repeat wash with 50 ml lysis buffer. Spin again and transfer beads to gravity column in a cold room. 5. Wash column with 20 ml W30. 6. Elute protein with 3x 10 ml EB. Analyse the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using the Bradford assay.
Purification step 2: Size-exclusion chromatography	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Concentrate the protein to 1 ml using a centrifugal concentrator with the appropriate MWCO. 2. Purify the protein further by Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) on a HiLoad Superdex S200 HR 16/60 column in SEC buffer at 1 ml/min. 3. Analyse fractions by SDS-PAGE. Pool fractions containing protein of desired purity and concentrate to 10-20 mg/ml, as measured by UV spectroscopy. 4. Assess quality of protein by LC-MS intact mass analysis. 5. Snap-freeze aliquots in thin-walled PCR tubes in liquid N₂, and store at -80°C.
Protein Yield	11 mg/L of culture

References

1. Vicogne J, Vollenweider D, Smith JR, Huang P, Frohman MA, Pessin JE. Asymmetric phospholipid distribution drives in vitro reconstituted SNARE-dependent membrane fusion. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 2006 Oct 3;103(40):14761–6.
2. Kennedy MJ, Davison IG, Robinson CG, Ehlers MD. Syntaxin-4 defines a domain for activity-dependent exocytosis in dendritic spines. *Cell*. 2010 Apr 30;141(3):524–35.
3. Mohanasundaram P, Shanmugam MM. Role of syntaxin 4 in activity-dependent exocytosis and synaptic plasticity in hippocampal neurons. *Sci Signal*. 2010 Oct 19;3(144):jc7.
4. Cheng WW, Zhu Q, Zhang HY. Identifying Risk Genes and Interpreting Pathogenesis for Parkinson's Disease by a Multiomics Analysis. *Genes*. 2020 Sep 21;11(9):E1100.
5. Zhao X, Guan Y, Liu F, Yan S, Wang Y, Hu M, et al. SNARE Proteins Mediate α -Synuclein Secretion via Multiple Vesicular Pathways. *Mol Neurobiol*. 2022 Jan;59(1):405–19.
6. Xie L, Zhu D, Dolai S, Liang T, Qin T, Kang Y, et al. Syntaxin-4 mediates exocytosis of pre-docked and newcomer insulin granules underlying biphasic glucose-stimulated insulin secretion in human pancreatic beta cells. *Diabetologia*. 2015 Jun;58(6):1250–9.
7. Oh E, Ahn M, Afelik S, Becker TC, Roep BO, Thurmond DC. Syntaxin 4 Expression in Pancreatic β -Cells Promotes Islet Function and Protects Functional β -Cell Mass. *Diabetes*. 2018 Dec;67(12):2626–39.
8. Merz KE, Hwang J, Zhou C, Veluthakal R, McCown EM, Hamilton A, et al. Enrichment of the exocytosis protein STX4 in skeletal muscle remediates peripheral insulin resistance and alters mitochondrial

dynamics via Drp1. Nat Commun. 2022 Jan 20;13(1):424.

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